

Treating Language As A Skill

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"The limits of my language are the limits of my world."

-Ludwig Wittgenstein

INTRODUCTION

"I ascribe a basic importance to the phenomenon of language. To speak means to be in a position to use a certain syntax, to grasp the morphology of this or that language, but it means above all to assume a culture, to support the weight of a civilization."

- Frantz Fanon

As has been long emphasized by various linguists that language learning is not just learning how to communicate but it also furthers a larger goal, that of cultural integration. All human knowledge that has helped the civilization forward, and has glorified the race, is preserved and circulated through language. Therefore the growth of language in the history of mankind as well the development of language ability in the life of an individual is really important.

Language abilities have however gained importance in recent times owing to the massive information dissemination resulting in knowledge explosion due to the globalisation. Whether they are social interactions, market transactions, academics, social work or polity, language abilities play a vital role. That is why in the life of an individual, language ability is the basic tool for his/her further development. A person acquires the mother tongue naturally and spontaneously

(unless some challenge), but he/she learns other languages consciously. The more languages one knows, the wider is his/her field of experience and influences. Most of the schools, therefore offer more than one language to their students. Some languages however, gain more importance than the rest, owing to their utility. English, for example has become the most important language in a developing country like India due to its prevalence in the country and in the rest of the world. Not only the schools and colleges but even personality grooming centers and various placement agencies give special importance to teaching English as a language. There is a great number of institutes which claim the development of English proficiency, yet many of our state run schools and colleges have not been able to develop it as per the desired standards. Let us have a look on how we teach the second language, English in our institutes.

Our formal classroom teaching emphasizes reading and writing exercises while developing language, whereas language acquisition in natural surroundings takes place spontaneously through listening and speaking. One who is a careful listener develops better language abilities and this is why a person who is challenged by hearing, does not learn to speak. Skinner argued that children learn language based on behaviourist enforcement principles by associating words with meanings. Correct references are positively

reinforced when the child realizes the communicative value of words and phrases. (Lemetyinen, H.2012, October24. Language Acquisition. SimplyPsychology. <https://www.simplypsychology.org/language.html>)

This is a clear indication of the fact that in order to be able to speak, one needs to listen first. Keeping this in mind, the C.B.S.E.board has introduced A.S.L. (assessment of speaking and listening) since 2012. The purpose behind the introduction of A.S.L. is to bring the language teaching situation closer to the natural language acquisition situation. Let us examine the two situations: (See below Table 1)

Thus we find that the sequence followed, in acquiring language in a natural way, is through listening-speaking-writing- and then reading; in case of formal language teaching, the sequence changes to writing-reading-and then speaking. Listening experiences are often insufficient. This is where the problem begins. A person who learns English as a second language in a formal way at school may be better in writing / spelling but feels conscious when it comes to speaking. If we want our learners to speak this language in a fluent and confident manner, we will have to bring the language teaching methods closer to language acquisition situation. Language is being treated

as any other technical subject in our institutes, where the technique of writing, spelling, syntax, nomenclature, etc. is given through many language drills. Thereby making the language more complicated for the learner. If we need a better result, we will have to treat language as a skill and not like a science. Like any other skill ,language can be learnt better through practice; from imperfect towards perfection; from apprenticeship to a habit. Yes, it has to be developed as a skill and then maintained as a habit.

We may compare the school environments of convents with that of the other schools, to see how the proficiency of the students are much better in case of the convents , which can largely be attributed to the school environment which provides the learners' with an exposure of listening English all around. We understand that it does not require extraordinary intelligence to learn a language; rather it comes through practice, imitation and repetition. Thus for the functional part of a language (eg English), we just need to provide an environment to the learner where s/he gets to listen that language for a long span of time. In higher classes, we may ask the learner to consciously search for opportunities of listening. I often suggest to my new batches

Table 1

Language acquisition (Mother tongue)	Language learning (Second language)
1. Listening takes place for the whole day	Listening takes place for a stipulated time
2. Speaking follows spontaneously	Writing is taught (alphabets, words)
3. Articulation attempts are encouraged through the communicative value	Learner is self conscious and has a lot of inhibitions..
4. Grammar/ linguistics are not taught. It comes through practice	Stress on syntax/ linguistics
5. Writing may or may not follow.	Writing is desired

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of learners to listen to the English news and the panel discussions, instead of reading a newspaper, on a regular basis. This exercise helps them as their auditory conditioning is achieved. This also adds to the exposure time of the students to the language on daily basis.

Language learning and the role of the teacher

There are certain methods which might be tried at different levels in teaching English as a second language. In order to give more exposure to listening, we may include classroom discussions, debates, elocutions, storytelling, dramatics and extempore speeches. While doing so, a teacher has to play a very important role by encouraging the learners with small incentives and appreciations. Most of the time, a language teacher is found to be criticizing the new learners who are already self-conscious due to their age (let's remember that in a natural language acquisition the learners are only two to three years old). We begin to teach English at an age when the learners are developing their self esteem, hence the language teacher has to deal in a psychological way. One small criticism results into such embarrassment to a learner in front of his peer group that often the learner is demotivated to speak this second language. It is painful to note that some English language teachers often humiliate the learners in classroom which is one of the greatest reasons of mental blocks that develop among the learners. It ruins the possibility of accepting the new language in a friendly manner in future. Also, it is very important for the teacher to connect the classroom activity to the real life situations or else the language remains closed up in the books. The language learnt through the classroom activities must be relatable to the life outside the

classroom. When the learner's get a communicative value in the real life functions, they would be encouraged to use the second language. I found it handy to refer to a show / online series in English which is popular among the learners to give a subtle sense of appreciation to those among the learners who subscribe it. We may ask them to watch the prescribed plays / listen audio forms of the prescribed stories, before we discuss them in the class. This not only reinforces the subject matter but also enhances the learners listening time.

Tap the personal time of the learner towards language learning

The classroom activity is not sufficient and also the time allotted to a language teacher, is not enough, a teacher must try to tap the personal time of the learners towards language learning by inspiring them towards listening to good audio-visuals, like documentaries, TED talks and important speeches by great historical personalities on the internet. Some quality television serials which inculcate good language abilities may be selected as the topic for classroom discussion to give recognition to the learners who subscribe to them. Thus, if the learners begin to give exposure to their ears to some good English in their personal time, it would enhance the learning automatically. With the appearance of tablets and mobile phones which are truly portable devices, language learning has got a full new arena of possibilities. More than anything else these are communication devices and therefore they may be positively utilized to enhance communication skills. English Language Teachers' Association of India, Kanpur chapter had recently organized a workshop on 'Mobile assisted language learning' (MALL) on 7th

February, 2017 in the premises of V.S.S.D. College, Kanpur. Mobile phones may be very judiciously encouraged by the teachers among the learners. For instance, mobile phone applications like English dictionary, Hindi-to-English dictionary, audio dictionary, Sudoku, idioms' games, synonym- antonym games, duolingo etc. can prove to be an important asset to the learners. Besides this, there are many language courses available online which may be utilised as an add on course.

Assignments

The learners may be given assignments which require them to function in English rather than just to write in English. For instance, they may be asked to teach younger/ junior children at home/ at the institution. In the remedial classes, the senior students may be asked to help the junior students in language learning. This will give them speaking opportunities in front of junior students where the inhibitions of articulating in a new language would be lesser. Some renowned schools like Loreto Convent, Calcutta, have been following this method of remedial teaching for long. Some other institutes inspire their students to join internships at different organizations during their vacations. This practice should not only be restricted to the professional courses but also be encouraged to be taken up by the students of pure language and humanities. This enables the learners to improve their functional English. Therefore, this should be encouraged even at junior classes. Any child above 14 years of age could be encouraged to take up such assignments. For instance, an NGO named 'Nandi Foundation' operating at Hyderabad has some school children assisting the foundation during the school summer vacations.

Language Labs

All good educational institutes do have language laboratories, but they are seldom utilized to their optimum level. Language labs like libraries have their worth only if they are exhaustively utilized. A lot of selected audio exercises can be given and speaking drills may be monitored in a language lab. Students should be motivated to use their language labs in their free periods. All spare time available to the student shouldn't be diverted towards sciences and mathematics, some at least, may be given to language learning. This is possible (as it is done in some residential schools) only when the head of the institution and other subject teachers understand the importance of language skills and accept it as an endeavor that would enhance students performance in other subjects as well.

Assessment methods

The evaluation of language abilities should not be based on only written examinations. At least, 40% of the evaluation should be made on the basis of speaking abilities. That is why the C.B.S.E. has introduced assessment of speaking and listening in collaboration with the Trinity College, London (source, cbseacademicmic.in/aslcorner.html). Many colleges and universities have a viva- voce examination for the assessment of the students ability of articulation which is given so much of weightage that a student is considered disqualified unless he clears the viva-voce (, despite his/her good percentile in the written examination) This method of examination does motivate the learners to improve the speaking ability, when followed with seriousness and integrity. If the viva- voce examinations are diluted in execution, students take it in a non serious mode and the purpose of

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these examinations are defeated. The common European Framework for Reference for Language, CEFR or CEFRL which is a guideline used to describe achievements of learner's of foreign language, emphasises on the assessment of the second language learners' learning outcomes through subjective means. We can not expect to assess the language learning outcomes through terminal written tests. Surprisingly some institutes in India test their language learners' through objective type MCQ, for the ease of preparing the results, where students with minimal language ability may chance to secure very good grades. When such students are required to use the language at functional level, they obviously fail.

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